

GENRE BASED APPROACH IN ONLINE LEARNING IN WRITING ANALYTICAL EXPOSITION TEXT

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Abstract: This study shares process genre-based approach and those who are taught by using non-PGBA learning through online learning. First, The application of Genre Based Approach makes students more assisted and helped through implementing the stages of Genre Based Approach. This approach is defined through the number of stages including Building Knowledge of The Field (BKOF), Modeling of the Text (MOT), Join Construction of the Text (JCOT), and Independent of Construction of the Text (ICOT). Second, mind mapping technique was popularized in the late of the 1960s and has been employed in many different areas since the development This technique was introduced as a note taking technique. In short, the mind map and genre-based approach enables the students to write more systematically.

INTRODUCTION

Even though students can write, read, and listen well in foreign language classes, the writing seems to be the hardest skill to learn. A writer should think about mechanics, grammar, writing style, and the difficulties of communicating what needs to be said. According to McCarrier, A., Pinnell, G. S. (2000), they stated that there are several processes in writing. Before beginning to write, a writer must consider

the intent of the writing, the intended reader, and the type or method of writing that will be used to convey the message. Then, when composing, technical and grammatical precision come into play. A writer reflects and evaluates during the process as the final step. If the text is more than a few words long, the writer rereads as he or she goes, viewing each sentence as a component of a larger text.

The objective of writing is to produce a kind of writing text. An analytical exposition text is one of the texts learnt in the eleventh year of high school. Analytical text is an argumentative text containing the view of the writer on a controversial subject. Analytical exposition text is a part of expository writing in kind of text genre. According to Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Indonesia, (2013) there four basic competences in learning writing; 1) transactional text, 2) formal letter, 3) analytical exposition text, and 4) personal letter.

Genre Based Approach provides the features of similar group of text based on the social context of the creation and use (Hyland, 2003:21). So, the use of this approach can help the students to create a selected kind of written or oral text. As Feez, S. & Joyce, (1998:40) describe that Genre Based Approach is an approach used in teaching language skill about the structure and grammar features of spoken and written texts.

In Addition, mind map has a natural organizational structure that radiates from the centre and use lines, symbols, key words, colour and images according to simple, brain-friendly concepts (Buzan 2005). A mind mapping converts a long list of monotonous information into a colourful, memorable and highly organized diagram that works in line with your brain’s natural way of doing things.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Graham et al. (2012) claimed that writing is a useful tool to read, connect and express oneself. It is an integral part of educational, social, social and municipal communication. It's used in different fields, which in many situations will facilitate citizens. In several areas of our everyday lives we find writings that have meaningful functions. Kristin Lems, Leah D. Miller (2010) stated it includes a thought process that requires a deep knowledge and practice to avoid misunderstandings between writer and reader. It includes thinking processes which involve an extensive understanding and practice. Writers are typically split with the readers at various times and locations. In addition Nunan (1991) stated writers must also make inferences about the appropriate information of readers, determine what to add, remove and predict future difficulties for readers. Writing is perceived by second language students as the most difficult master's skill. The problem is to create and coordinate ideas and translate them into a legible text. Richards & Renandya (2002) stated that the skills of writing are very complex because writers are concerned with greater planning and organizational skills, also with lower levels like grammar, punctuation, word choice, etc.

b. Writing opens opportunities to learn

Writing as a discovery process gives authors the ability to discover concepts and viewpoints. It can understand religions and values. In addition, the writing process extends the experience of authors and changes their thought. It also leads to the efficient generalization, sentence and rational thinking.

c. Writing nurtures personal development

Writing increases trust, handles the self-affairs of authors, monitors self- progress, recognizes beliefs, develops goals, specifies

concerns and succeeds. They will evolve and mature as writers acquire knowledge. Also, writing can help authors have certain outlets in their lives. The ability to communicate well.

d. Writing helps to establish relationships

It helps preserve relationships with people or society by being able to write well and to create friendly written voices. Positive relationships can effectually build on the ability to choose positive terms, to remove negative ideas and to polish sentences.

e. Writing helps school and workplace success

For college and workplace success, writing is important. The ability to write well would help students to try to learn and share ideas. In order to evaluate their awareness, it is necessary not only to learn a language, but also for all subjects. In this work, writing allows you to think more about and write about real issues, including papers, e-mails, offers, etc.

4. Problem in Writing

According to (Byrne 1993), there are some difficulties related to writing; psychology, linguistic and cognitive difficulties. The first is the psychological difficulty of how to express the idea. According to (Trotman 2006) writing is having a message and communicating it successfully to others. Students need ideas and then arrange them in a good manner in order to deliver the message to the reader successfully. The second difficulty is dealing with linguistic. There is linguistic difficulty in that the language used in written language. The written language differs from the spoken language. In written language, there are lies grammatical rules that should be considered. The third difficulty is related to cognitive difficulty in which the students must organize their ideas on text with signal words to make the sequence of paragraphs well arranged.

Teaching and Learning writing

Curriculum 2013 has been applied since 2014 in order to replace the previous curriculum: Kurikulum Tingkat Satuan Pendidikan (KTSP). In the series of national curriculum policy is stated that teaching and learning processes at schools should build activities that engage students in the development of their higherorder thinking skills (HOTS). Regarding to teaching and learning writing in senior high school, in Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan RI no. 81 Tahun 2013 tentang Implementasi Kurikulum students are demanded to think logically, systematically, inductively, and think deductively using the information that they had. This curriculum also states that the teaching of writing should emphasize on comprehending various kinds of texts and increase students' mastery on writing ability.

e. Using the computer

There are many advantages of using a machine to teach writing:

- 1) A word processing program eliminates the challenge of bad handwriting that certain students have.
- 2) A word processing program enables the computer user to edit his or her documents quickly and easily.
- 3) Spellcheckers will make the work of correcting spelling easier.
- 4) A digital screen will be more noticeable to the whole community than a sheet of paper while students are collaborating in groups.

4. The Technique of Teaching Writing

Brown (2001) asserts that there are four categories of techniques for teaching writing. That are the four categories:

a. Imitative Writing

The accurate spell ability falls into this category. Students must master the universal, fundamental job of writing letters, vocabulary, punctuation, and short sentences. Imitative writing is a writing form that elementary students do.

b. Intensive (controlled writing)

Most evaluation activities in this group are more concerned with focusing on a type and are tightly regulated by the text template. In the level of sentences, students must generate adequate vocabulary within a context, collocation, idioms, and proper grammatical features. Senior High Schoolis included in this grouping.

c. Responsive Writing

Students must execute a minimal debate level at this level. It means that students must construct a two- or three-paragraph linked series. It reflects on the debate norms that will help the written text accomplish its goal. It also put a strong emphasis on sense and significance. This writing ability is normally reserved for Students of Senior High School.

d. Extensive Writing

Extensive learning entails mastering both writing techniques and methods for a variety of uses, including essays, term papers, and theses. The writers concentrate on reaching a goal, arranging and evolving concepts objectively, illustrating ideas with descriptions, and showing syntactical consistency. In addition, according to (Hyland 2008) there is a four- stage technique as an emphasis on a language structure in teaching writing. The first is familiarization which means that students are taught certain grammar, and vocabulary usually through a text. The second type is controlled writing, in which students manipulate

pre-determined patterns, which are frequently derived from substitution tables. The third is process genre based approach in which the students try to imitate model of the texts. The last is free writing where the students apply the pattern they have constructed to write an essay, letter and so forth. It can be concluded that students have to practice a lot to write well. By practicing, students will reach the next level of writing.

Online learning is a form of distance learning or distance education that has long been part of the American education system and has become the largest distance learning sector in recent years (Bartley, S. J., & Golek 2004). The application of Genre Based Approach makes students more assisted and helped through implementing the stages of Genre Based Approach. This approach is defined through the number of stages including Building Knowledge of The Field (BKOF), Modeling of the Text (MOT), Join Construction of the Text (JCOT), and Independent of Construction of the Text (ICOT). These stages provide several steps in cycles in order to help students to be easy to learn and comprehend the different kind of text. In other words, this approach allows students to learn the kind of text in relation of purpose, social context, and form and language feature of text.

While the students were watching the video, teacher explained and translated the sentences to Indonesian to make the students were easier to understand the content of the video. Teacher prepared the students with a text of analytical exposition. Teacher showed the text by using Prezi. The teacher built the students' knowledge, cultural context, discussed grammatical pattern of the text, explained generic structure of the text, social function. Based on the exercise result, the

teacher did this stage well. However, one drawback that the teacher did not do in this stage was building students’ vocabularies.

In MOT stage, the teacher implemented the MOT stage. The English teacher played a good role in this stage. The teacher read the text loudly, translated or interpreted the text to the students. The students listened to the teacher. Then, the teacher asked one of students to read it. In reading activity, the English teachers asked some questions to the students about the reading text and discussed the content of the text together. The teacher and students analyzed the generic structure, the social function, the grammatical pattern of the text.

Next, JCOT is the stage where the students try to begin to construct a text collaboratively in pair or group in Paddlet. In this section, the teacher gave instruction to the students to do activity in class. The students constructed a text of analytical exposition as well as they can in pair. They shared their idea, opinion in group. While the students were doing their activity, the teacher provided a help, a correction to the students’ work.

In ICOT, the teacher did not discuss the students’ personal assignments because of limited time in class. The final objectives of the implementation of Genre Based Approach are to provide students to be more successful in writing a whole of text type and to help students to make sense of language structure, language feature, and composition of the text (Brook in Emilia, 2015: 61). In other words, due to the expectations of Genre Based Approach, the students are expected to be able in creating the selected kind of text type. This approach provides students with guide practice as they develop language skill for meaningful communication through the whole text

(Adapted from Irmawati, 2011)

Mind mapping is a learning technique that was developed by Tony Buzan, a famous British psychologist. This mind mapping technique was popularized in the late of the 1960s and has been employed in many different areas since the development (Wang, 2010). This technique was introduced as a note taking technique. For all his attempts in developing mind mapping, Buzan has given a very useful technique to be learnt and used by students in a learning process.

CONCLUSION

In the English teaching and learning process, especially in writing, the English teacher should be creative in selecting and applying appropriate techniques which can build the students motivation and help students to reach their successful learning of English. For this reason, the teachers are suggested to use text-based approach in the teaching writing activities for building and increasing students’ motivation in writing ability. Students can be more motivated to learn, increase the writing ability and finally reach their success in the English learning. Based on this research, the effect of text-based approach in the teaching and learning process of writing helps students to practice and increase their writing ability and also helps them to build their motivation in English writing processes.

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